

Least squares approximation of ECG signals with rational functions

Software_01: prep.f95

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1. Abstract

This description is closely related to an **older article** of the same main title [1], reading this article will make it easier to understand more. It mostly discusses the working principle of our ECG Feature Extraction **progr1-123** program (which is part of the FEX3-ECG program system). This program system does not extract the features (FEX) automatically, but with frequent operator interaction. Between the steps, he draws the diagram necessary for further decisions, and based on this, the operator determines the next step of the program.

In the following description, we deal with the operation and use of the preparation program (**prep**) associated with this program (**progr1-123**). In the 4.12. *Preparation* section of the mentioned article [1], we have already briefly described the program (**prep**):

We use a preparatory program (**prep**) to cut out the desired periods of the signal to be approximated from the raw ECG signals. First, we - temporarily - remove **baseline** wander and higher frequency noise with frequency filters. Then, similarly to a method described below $\{\max. \text{length of a vector} = \text{SQRT}(v_x^2 + v_y^2 + v_z^2)\}$, we find the locations of the QRS (the time values of the maximum activity point of the ECG signal). Then, by marking the beginnings of the P waves, we get the **initial** baseline segments of each period. Finally, after omitting noise filtering - we plot the periods of the signal and their **initial** baseline segments with MS_EXCEL. Now, the entire baseline can be moved by grabbing a point on the baseline segment using the mouse. It is advisable to first choose the captured point close to the beginning of the baseline segment, then - in response to an MS_EXCEL question - the beginning of the line will move and the end will remain in place. Then the same will happen at a point close to the end. This way we can **accurately** set the standard **final** baseline used in cardiology.

In what follows, we use the **original signal** without the temporary filters.

2. We repeat and supplement some information from the mentioned above article [1]:

The **Fortran** we use {[1] 4.4 *The norm and tools used for approximation*} and its environment:

64 bit processor, Windows 7 Professional with Service Pack 1

GNU Fortran (GCC) 4.8.1 with 0.6.2-mingw32-beta-20131004-1

This compiler is not Fortran IV or Fortran 66: "The GNU Fortran compiler supports the Fortran 77, 90 and 95 standards completely, parts of the Fortran 2003 and Fortran 2008 standards, and several vendor extensions" [3]. In addition to these modern improvements, we can use older subroutines, such as those in MINPACK, without changing the source code!

Our records uploaded in the topic of the main title can be accessed by the following search:

<https://zenodo.org/search?q=creators.name%3A%20%22Kobzos%2C%20Laszlo%22&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=bestmatch>

Since this program-system **does not automatically calculate the features** (FEX), but with frequent operator interaction, we create **diagrams** for them, using **MS_EXCEL** or **GNU Octave** [4]. The **transfer of information** between the parts of our program system usually takes place in text files. So are the above programs. In these text files, we used a **decimal point** (for GNU Octave) or a **decimal comma** (for MS_EXCEL). Any text editor can be used to transform them, replacing all commas with points or vice versa.

The source code of our programs is usually provided with many **comments** for their use and possible modifications. The comments are in Hungarian. The same goes for text outputs. We hope that the English language **program descriptions** and **user guides** will be of sufficient help to understand our programs.

We use two types of character encoding:

- For Windows text files and comments: Windows-1250
- For Windows Command Prompt (~DOS) files: OEM 852

If we use Notepad++ : Encoding | Character sets | Central European | ...

The source of the ECG data used { [1] 4.5 *Data* } :

Our ECG data comes from the **PhysioNet database** [2]. From this database, 549 **anonymized** ECG data of 290 individuals can be accessed by selecting PTB. In addition to the signals, the “PTB Diagnostic ECG Database” contains other data, as well (such as: age, sex and diagnosis of the individuals, ...). Signals are sampled at 1 kHz (i.e. 1 sample per 1 millisecond), and a 1mV signal corresponds to a quantisation level of 2000. Although our method is independent of the lead system, we have mainly investigated 3 leads of the **Frank system** (vx, vy and vz; sometimes only x, y and z). Using Dower or inverse-Dower matrix transformations, the data of the conventional 12-lead system can be calculated from the Frank lead system data, and vice versa [5, 6].

The original ECG signals: DOI: <https://doi.org/10.13026/C28C71> License: Open Data Commons Attribution License v1.0

We do not deal with cases of **arrhythmia**, because these signs belong to the "should consult a cardiologist" category.

A commonly used method to extract the feature data (FEX, Feature Extraction): "A common method is to approximate the signal using a function with parameters that can be set, so that the difference between the signal and the **shapes** of the function (in the biologically relevant parts) is small. Then the parameters of the function that approximate the signal will be considered to be characteristic of it. For this purpose, we have chosen rational functions." For approximation, the rational function was written in the root factor form { [1] 4.1. *The approximation function* }. The roots of the denominator and the numerator are called poles and zeros, respectively.

Identifying the periods used { [1] 5. **Results**, first paragraph } :

The signals tested are denoted as follows: s... = serial number, p... = patient number. For example "s0025_p005". If we want to be more precise about the location within the record, we also indicate the lead and the location of the QRS. For example “s0025_p005, vz, 7009”.

The coordinate system used { [1] 4.6. *The coordinate system used* } :

The **x-axis** (t-axis) of a period of a lead was determined with a method usually **used in cardiology**. That is, in the signal-free part before the P wave of the period, we identify a location where the noise is limited, or filter out the noise by “looking”, and we mark the starting point of the baseline. The other point of the

baseline is similarly determined at the next P wave. The line passing through these two points is called the **baseline**.

The time value of the maximum point of the signal energy (proportional to the square of the voltage) was chosen as the **origin**. This point is always within the QRS-complex. In more detail: In the case of a **Frank lead** system, since it is orthogonal in space, we used the Pythagorean Theorem to determine the curve of the voltage vector length from the vx vy vz leads. Its maximum indicates the maximum activity of the electrical signal of the heart. Because of the noise on the leads, we instead cut the curve at 95% of the maximum voltage vector and choose the middle point between the two intersections as the time value of the origin. Since this does not usually coincide with the location of the sampling point, we round to the nearest location.

If we do not use a Frank lead system, but a 12-lead system, then the location of the origin can be determined in the same way using the (nearly perpendicular) V6, II and $-0.5 \times V2$ leads [7].

Addendum to this: In programs, the last character of the variable name is often **A** or **R**. This usually means **Absolute** or **Relative**. For example: `i_P1_locA`. For the ECG signal downloaded from the database, the character **A** indicates the distance calculated from the starting point of the signal, while **R** indicates the distance calculated from the starting point of the selected period (P, QRS and T). In those programs that deal with only one period, **A** indicates the distance from the beginning of the period, while **R** indicates the (signed) distance from the QRS wave.

We wrote at the beginning of all our programs written in Fortran (.f95) that we do not use automatic type declaration (**implicit none**). But **usually** the first letter of **INTEGER** variables is "I, J, K, L, M, or N". The **LOGICAL** variables **usually** start with "log_" and **CHARACTER** variables with "ch".

The number of parameters of the above-mentioned function is often listed in programs, data files and diagrams. For example, variable names: `ch_fajt12`, `i_P_fajt1`, `i_P_fajt2`, `i_fajt2`. For example in figures: P35 "stands for wave P, 3 is the number of parameters of the numerator (including the leading coefficient **d**), while 5 is the number of pole **pairs** (factors) of the denominator. Thus, the number of parameters of the approximation is $3 + 2 \times 5 = 13$."

The two six-character numbers in the data files and in the figures are the timestamp. This 2×6 digit number (yymmdd hhmmss) means "year month day hour minute second".

In our figures containing a single period:

- On the millimeter-scale paper commonly used in ECG machines, the 1×1 mm square of ECG signals (so-called "small square") this corresponds to 40 points (40 ms) \times 200 points (0.1 mV) in our drawings. This 40 points \times 200 points grid - enlarged according to the size of the figure - shown on all our diagrams containing ECG signals.

- Drawing the imaginary values of the roots on the same diagram as the ECG signals we multiplied them by 50, 70, 7 and 50 for the P, QRS, T and Ta waves, respectively (for old ECG signals: 50, 100, 10, -).

- In the figures, the poles are marked with **x** and the zeros with **o**.

- In the figures, only one of the two conjugated complex roots was shown, namely always the one falling towards the momentary value of the signal.

3. Program Description

The purpose of the program is to select 5 periods from the "vx, vy, vz" stream and define their baselines.

Input UNITS:

- keyboard: the location of the start of two P waves, 4× resuming the pending program
- 101 filters data
- 103 the baselines corrections
- 121 the raw ECG from a file (stream.xyz)

Output UNITS:

- screen
- 124 print for marking P waves and correction of baselines (EXCEL)
- 126 the number of samples per period, approx. where are the qrs
- 128 In 5 rows: the locations and values of the P waves (baseline), the approx. location of the QRS wave

STATEMENT FUNCTION:

f_alapv_st_fv(i_form_par) To calculate the points of a line passing through two points.

01~ ~~~ chapter

Reading in the data of the **filters**.

The baseline filter:

prep-BL-ehat2.txt ==> bln_filt(:)

Octave firls 0.0 0.5 0.9 500.0 Hz, 10800+1 low-pass filter

The noise filter:

44-40-485-511-22-filter.txt ==> zaj_filt(:)

Octave remez 0.0 40.0 48.5 500.0 Hz, 510+1 low-pass filter

02~ ~~~ chapter

Writing out the number of points to be **skipped** at the beginning of the long ECG signal (many periods):

"Az EKG jel elején kihagyandó pontok száma:" "Number of points to skip at the beginning of the ECG signal:"

ix_offs ==> screen

Writing out the number of points to be **processed** of the long ECG signal (many periods):

"Az EKG jel most feldolgozandó hossza:"

"The length of the ECG signal to be processed now in points:"

n_ekg ==> screen

Allocations, zeroings.

Reading in **data of ECG**. (vx, vy, vz leads, n_ekg point)

stream.xyz ==> ekg_xyz(:,:)

03~ ~~~ chapter

Filterings:

ekg_xyz(:,:) ==> **noise filter** ==> zsz_xyz(:,:)

zsz_xyz(:,:) ==> **baseline filter** ==> bln_xyz(:,:)

Note: This baseline is only used temporarily.

04~ ~~~ chapter

We subtract the wandering baseline from the wandering ECG signal:

zsz_xyz(:,:) - bln_xyz(:,:) ==> alf_xyz(:,:)

Thus, horizontal lines are obtained by connecting the **same points of the waves** (P-P-P..., QRS-QRS-QRS...) in their periods of the examined signal (that is, they are at the **same height**).

By convention, the height of the **beginnings of P** waves should be **set to zero**.

alf_xyz(:,:) ==> bln.txt all three leads (Frank lead system)

Then we plot the bln.txt signal using MS_EXCEL.

'1. A kirajzolt jel második QRS-e előtti és utáni'

Before and after the second QRS of the drawn signal

' P hullámok kezdeteinek helyét beírjuk, DE '

the location of the beginnings of P waves is entered, BUT

' még ENTER nélkül!'

without ENTER yet!

'2. lépünk ki az MS_EXCEL-ből'

Close MS_EXCEL,

'3. majd most az ENTER'

and now ENTER.

keyboard ==> i_P1_locA, i_P2_locA (We will need the value of the variable i_P2_locA later.)

alf_xyz(:, i_P1_locA) ==> offs(:) all three leads

Then we correct the signal with the value of the offset:

alf_xyz(:, :) - offs(:) ==> req_xyz(:,:) all three leads

05~ ~~~ chapter

We calculate the **vector length function** of the ECG signal:

```
sqrt(req_xyz(x,:)² + req_xyz(y,:)² + req_xyz(z,:)²) ==> vlo_xyz(:)
```

We find the value of the maximum of the function:

```
v_max
```

The 70% of this maximum value:

```
v_szint
```

We find the **intersection** points of "the line with height **v_szint**" and "the **function** above".

The arithmetic centers of the ascending and descending intersections will be the approx. locations of the QRS:

```
(i_sz_ala + i_sz_fole) / 2 ==> i_qrsA (:)
```

The location of the first and last QRS is not stored (it might not belong to a complete period).

In the following, we only use the original ECG signal!

06~ ~~~ chapter

Writing out the vector length function:

```
vlo_xyz(:) ==> bln.txt
```

Writing out on the screen:

The number of QRSs and the location of the first QRS found to be valid:

```
nb_qrs, i_qrsA(1) ==> screen
```

If the number of QRS is greater than 5, we reduce it to 5.

Writing out the location of the 5 QRS:

```
i_qrsA(:) ==> screen
```

We check that we have marked the correct pre-QRS location as the first P location? If not, EXIT

Writing out on the screen:

The **average QRS distance** and, based on this, the **heart rate**:

```
(i_qrsA(5) - i_qrsA(1)) / 4 ==> i_seg1 ==> screen (if (nb_qrs .EQ. 5))
```

```
60000/i_seg ==> screen
```

Next, let's look at the bln.txt (vector length) signal plotted with MS_EXCEL as a check.

07~ ~~~ chapter

The "approx." locations of the QRS of the periods are already known for our set goal. Approx. locations of P waves can also be calculated. For this, we know

that the signal is approximately periodic, since we have ruled out arrhythmia at the moment.

We introduce three signal sections:

$i_111 = i_P2_locA - i_P1_locA + 1$ spacing of P waves
 $i_222 = i_111 + 2 * i_wider$ the length of the drawn section of the baseline
 $i_333 = i_111 + i_balsz + i_jobbsz$ the length of the signal period used hereafter

Note: The location of the second and third,... P waves could be calculated more precisely based on the location of the next QRS. We will not use this because we will draw the marks to precisely set the position of the baseline. That is, the places calculated from the QRS in each period are the same.

The starting points of the baseline sections:

$i_P1_locA + i_qrsA(:) - i_qrsA(1) ==> i_e_xyzA(:)$

The end points of the baseline sections:

$i_P2_locA + i_qrsA(:) - i_qrsA(1) ==> i_v_xyzA(:)$

So, these points are close to the beginnings of P waves.

08~ ~~~ chapter

Cycle start. ===== For leads vx, vy and vz. (1, 2 and 3)

Writing out on the screen:

$ic_xyz ==> screen$ (cycle variable)

In the following, we will fill in a **table** (CH_bl(:,:)), draw it with MS_EXCEL, and then make the final adjustment of the baselines.

The character array of the baseline is filled with 21 "0" characters:

'0000000000000000000000' ==> CH_bl(:,:)

The indices of the rows of this table change according to the value of time. The consecutive periods of the signal are listed in the A C E G I column. Next to them, in columns B D F H J, they have their approximate baseline.

The general formula of a line passing through two points: $y = (y2 - y1) * (x - x1) / (x2 - x1) + y1$

An example for column D:

A point of the baseline in the table (21 characters): $=(D2-D1)*0038/0885+D1$

One line down: $=(D2-D1)*0039/0885+D1$

The two points (x1, x2) are approx. the "beginning of the P wave" before and after the QRS. D1 and D2 are the values of the signal at these points. For simplicity, we will put these values in the first two positions of column D. These values change as we move the line, so that final baselines can be set.

The signal-baseline pairs are we raise by 1000, 2000,... points for visibility (i_fugg_eltol).

09~ ~ ~ chapter

The limits of the i_111 section are set within the periods of the ECG signal ("R" relative places from the beginning of the period):

1 + i_balsz ==> i_tolR

i_111 + i_balsz ==> i_iggR

Then we load the "baseline columns" (B D ...) of the array (CH_bl(:,:)) described above in a cycle..

The inner cycle is i_222 long due to the visibility of the baseline.

10~ ~ ~ chapter

We divide the original ECG signal into periods of length i_333. For this, we know the approx. location of the beginnings of the P waves.

ekg_xyz(:,:) ==> ecg_sct(:,:)

Two points of the (to be corrected) baseline: the approx. **location** and **value** of the P wave before and after the QRS of this signal.

Based on this, we set parameter 4 of the STATEMENT FUNCTION: ialapv_kx, ialapv_vx, alapv_k_y, alapv_v_y.

We calculate the baseline based on the STATEMENT FUNCTION values:

f_alapv_st_fv(:) ==> ecg_bln(:,:)

By subtracting this baseline, we get column (A C ...) of the (CH_bl(:,:)) array.

As we wrote above: The signal-baseline pairs on the figure are we raise by 1000, 2000,... points for visibility (i_fugg_eltol).

ecg_sct(:,:) - ecg_bln(:,:) + r_fugg_eltol ==> ecg_rdy(:,:)

The values of the first 4 positions of the baselines still need to be set:

Staying with the above example, D1 and D2 are known. We will store their changes, i.e. the corrections, in locations D3 and D4.

(Note: For the values placed in D1 and D2, we calculated with the noise-filtered signal.)

We write out the data of the ECG periods and baselines into the bln.txt file:

ecg_rdy(:,:), CH_bl(:,:) ==> bln.txt

11~ ~ ~ chapter

What needs to be done in the MS_EXCEL drawing:

- '1. állítsuk be az alapvonalakat'
- '2. mentjük el a beállított táblázatot (.xls)'
- '3. töröljük ki a rajzot'
- '4. töröljük ki az EKG oszlopokat(A, C, E...)'
- '5. állítsuk be hány tizedes legyen'
- '6. másoljuk ki a 3. 4. sor adatait a prep-xyz.txt file-ba'

let's set the baselines (See below: User Guide)

save it all (.xls)

delete the drawing

delete the ECG columns (A, C, E...)

let's set the number of decimal places

copy the data of the 3rd and 4th lines into the prep-xyz.txt file. The

transfer of vx to the 2nd and 3rd rows

(then vy to the 5th and 6th rows,

and finally to the vz to the 8th and 9th rows)

'végül MS_EXCEL kilépés, vissza a PREP-be: 1 karakter'

finally MS_EXCEL exit, back to PREP: 1 character

End of cycle.=====For leads vx, vy and vz. (1, 2 and 3)

12~ ~~~ chapter

We reading in the corrections from the prep-xyz.txt file:

prep-xyz.txt ==> corr_e_xyz(:,:) and

prep-xyz.txt ==> corr_v_xyz(:,:)

Making corrections:

ekg_xyz(:,:) + corr_e_xyz(:,:) ==> crt_e_xyz(:,:)

ekg_xyz(:,:) + corr_v_xyz(:,:) ==> crt_v_xyz(:,:)

13~ ~~~ chapter

We write out the data into 2 files.

How many ECG points is the period long:

i_333 ==> one111per.txt

Within this, where will be the approx. location of the QRS:

i_qrsA(1) - i_P1_locA + i_balsz + 1 ==> one111per.txt

Then the next 5 lines to the qrs_index.txt file, 3 + 3×2 values in each row. The approx. location of the QRS, the starting and ending location of the baseline, and then the values here of the three leads:

i_qrsA(:) + ix_offs, i_e_xyzA(:) + ix_offs, i_v_xyzA(:) + ix_offs, (crt_e_xyz(:,:), crt_v_xyz(:,:)) ==> qrs_index.txt

Only this data will be used from now on. So, for example, we do not take advantage of the fact that the 2 points are near the P waves.

End of run.

=====

14~ ~~~ chapter

subroutine szur_s (ekg_s, filt_s, i_tap_s)

The input parameters are respectively: the three leads of the ECG signal, the FIR filter coefficients, the number of filter coefficients.

The n_ekg is a global variable.

The output parameter is also ekg_s.

End of program.

3. User Guide

In the older version of the program, there were a few more input parameters. We usually changed them very rarely. For example, for the points to be omitted from the beginning of the stream (ix_offs), this became 0. Or the number of signal points of the "long" EKG stream to be scanned (n_ekg), this turned out to be 20000. But, if necessary, they can be changed. Although some of them require changing another parameter. (Then compiling and testing.)

Let's copy the current file containing the data of the **PhysioNet database** [2] (Frank lead system) into the directory of the prep.exe file. Then rename it (for example the S0038LRE.XYZ) always to **stream.xyz**. Because the program always expects the ECG input file with this name {02~ ~}.

Program outputs:

Writing out the number of points to be **skipped** at the beginning of the long ECG signal (many periods):

"Az EKG jel elején kihagyandó pontok száma:"

ix_offs ==> screen (default: 0)

Writing out the number of points to be **processed** of the long ECG signal (many periods):

"Az EKG jel most feldolgozandó hossza:"

n_ekg ==> screen (default: 20000)

'1. A kirajzolt jel második QRS-e előtti és utáni'

' P hullámok kezdeteinek helyét beírjuk, DE '

' még ENTER nélkül!'

'2. lépünk ki az MS_EXCEL-ből'

'3. majd most az ENTER'

Before and after the second QRS of the drawn signal

the location of the beginnings of P waves is entered, BUT

without ENTER yet!

Close MS_EXCEL,

and now ENTER.

Based on the MS_EXCEL drawing, we used the following values for the ECG signal above: 6311 7196 (free format)

Program outputs:

Writing out the vector length function:

```
vlo_xyz(:) ==> bln.txt
```

Writing out on the screen:

The number of QRS-s and the location of the first QRS found to be valid:

```
nb_qrs, i_qrsA(1) ==> screen
```

(when testing: 9 6525)

If the number of QRS is greater than 5, we reduce it to 5.

Writing out the location of the 5 QRS:

```
i_qrsA(:) ==> screen
```

(when testing: 6525 7400 8279 9155 10013)

We check that we have marked the correct pre-QRS location as the first P location? If not, EXIT.

Writing out on the screen:

The average QRS distance and, based on this, the heart rate

```
i_qrsA(5) - i_qrsA(1) / 4 ==> i_seg1 ==> screen ( if (nb_qrs .EQ. 5) )
```

(when testing: 872)

```
60000/i_seg ==> screen
```

(when testing: 68)

Next, let's look at the bln.txt (vector length) signal plotted with MS_EXCEL as a check.

Cycle start.=====For leads vx, vy and vz. (1, 2 and 3)

Program outputs:

Writing out on the screen:

```
ic_xyz ==> screen (cycle variable)
```

(when testing: 1, later 2 3)

What needs to be done in the MS_EXCEL drawing:

'1. állítsuk be az alapvonalakat'

let's set the baselines (See below: **Final setting of ...**)

'2. mentsük el a beállított táblázatot (.xls)'

save it all (.xls) (we save x to: bln-----x.xls)

'3. töröljük ki a rajzot'

delete the drawing

'4. töröljük ki az EKG oszlopokat(A, C, E...)'

delete the ECG columns (A, C, E...)

'5. állítsuk be hány tizedes legyen'

let's set the number of decimal places

'6. másoljuk ki a 3. 4. sor adatait a prep-xyz.txt file-ba'

copy the data of the 3rd and 4th lines into the prep-xyz.txt file. The transfer of vx to the 2nd and 3rd rows

(then vy to the 5th and 6th rows,
and finally to the vz to the 8th and 9th rows)

'végül MS_EXCEL kilépés, vissza a PREP-be: 1 karakter' finally MS_EXCEL exit, back to PREP: 1 character

End of cycle.=====For leads vx, vy and vz (1, 2 and 3).

Program outputs:

Finally, we write the results to the files "one111per.txt" and "qrs_index.txt"

End of program.

Final setting of the baselines in the MS_EXCEL drawing:

Open the bln.txt file.

Open the chart settings window with the "Chart Wizard" icon.

Select the "line".

Select the upper-left option from "Chart sug-type".

Finish.

A drawing containing the ECG signals and approx. baselines will then open.

We can delete the "Legend" and the "Category Axis" numbers.

Let's pull it apart the drawing horizontally to the two edges of the screen. (horizontal zoom)

Let's pull the figure up completely. And pull down the lower edge of the drawing to about the 170th row. (vertical zoom)

Thus, the figure became appropriately large.

The individual ECG signals and the corresponding approx. baselines are drawn 1000 points above each other.

Find the beginning of the P wave of the bottom signal in the figure.

The corresponding approximate baseline is numbered "Series 2" (usually magenta).

Any **point** of the baseline can be **moved** up and down, but then the **baseline will not move yet!**

Now it is advisable to select the point for moving at the **starting point of the left P wave.**

- To move this point of the baseline, click the mouse here on the line, then the line will be selected.

- Then again in the same place. Be careful not to click directly after the first click, because that would be a double-click. The point is then selected. A small

square will appear with an up and down arrow. This is approx. it looks like this, slightly enlarged:

- For the third time, we can **drag the point up and down** by holding down the left mouse button. Since the signal is usually noisy, the vertical position must be adjusted by visual inspection.

By releasing the left mouse button in the appropriate place, a window will appear with title: **Goal Seek**

You have to answer in the **By changing cell:** field, now this: B1. Because cell B1 contains the value of the left-point of the lowest baseline (a straight line passing through two points).

By typing this (and Enter), you will now see the **new location of the straight line**. Because MS_EXCEL changed the value of cell B1 and thus the position of the straight line.

Similarly, at the beginning of the P wave after the QRS. But here the answer is B2. Because this point is closer to the right-hand fixed point of the straight line. It is advisable to do the adjustment first at the beginning of the left P and secondly at the beginning of the right P.

Next is the ECG+baseline pair one up. Here the method is completely similar, but now the two answers are: D1 and D2.

And so on, up to the top pair.

Note: Help for the letter of the column: The letter in the first line (**Set cell**) of **Goal Seek**: is the correct one. (if it is e.g. D220, then D1 or D2 is the correct answer).

Note: The movement of the baseline can be made continuous and visible throughout, if the content of cell B1 is continuously increased. In older MS_EXCEL, this is made possible by continuously pressing the F4 key (plus an auxiliary cell) {in newer MS_EXCEL, CTRL+Y (Repeats the last command or action, if possible)}. We didn't use this later.

4. References

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